

Fixity Checking a Large Climate Data Archive

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Motivation

Climate and Earth Observation sciences rely on consistent large data sets. The Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA) has an archive of over 3PB of data, the bulk of which is the output from climate models and numerical weather prediction systems, and earth observation datasets.

It is important to make sure these data are fixity checked because:

- Corruption can disrupt or services that rely on data consistency.
- Checks gives a quantifiable measure of trust in repository systems.
- Auditing provides traceability for data results, for example proving a file was the same 3 years ago.

File sets

The CEDA archive is divided into file sets for the purpose of file management operations, such as backup, media migration and file fixity checking. File sets are non-overlapping; every file is in one and only one file set. To ensure practical management each file set is limited to no more than 40TB in size and no more than around 3 million files. File sets going over these limits are split into small units.

Audits

An audit is a complete read operation of all the files in a file set. We aim to audit all file sets every 3 months. The audit provides a record of what is in the archive, a check for file corruption and flags files with other problems, for example bad permission attributes.

The audit cycle

Every hour an audit is submitted to the queue. For each audit:

1. The file set with the least up to date audit is found.
2. The file set is divided into file lists so that no list has more than 100000 files or is bigger than 100GB.
3. Each file list is used as input for a job constructing a portion of the checkm file.
4. A compilation process stitches together the final checkm file and submits it to the audit database.
5. The results are compared to the last audit, noting numbers of new, modified, deleted and corrupt files.

A daily digest is emailed to the archive manager drawing attention to problems.

Results

In 2014, 13 corrupt files were detected, and in 2015, 10 corrupt files were detected among the 180 million files in the archive. It is hard to pinpoint the causes of the corruption. In the past year several corruption events have shown a 2k block of bad data suggesting a systematic problem. It is still relatively rare, and easily recoverable from backups.

The images shown here are an example of how the corruption can manifest in a single area of a single field in file.

Conclusions

- It is important not to simply rely on the internal integrity checking mechanisms in hardware systems. These systems are fallible like everything else.
- Corruption is rare on the current JASMIN storage system.
- Future systems need to be monitored closely if we are to have confidence in their fixity.

Checkm files

Checkm files are used as a simple file manifest format, see example below. This provides a record of archive state and can be compared to the previous audit.

```
# scanning path /datacentre/archvol/pan2/archive/urgent
# audit id: 24387
# generated 2016-04-02 07:28:00.252514
#
# Filename | Algorithm | Digest | Length | ModTime
# DIR /datacentre/archvol/pan2/archive/urgent/data
# DIR /datacentre/archvol/pan2/archive/urgent/data/gaspol
data/gaspol/.summary | md5 | 8e557787fea4a101fc6100b2f74e656b | 475 | 2010-11-08T07:16:41Z
data/gaspol/00README | md5 | 3b74a0bfb6e6fe329de6db16e90c39a4 | 227 | 2003-02-13T17:02:20Z
data/gaspol/Data_Summary.html | md5 | b38fa5bc4c0d768e01f24ffb5e8dff4e | 132 | 2003-02-14T14:22:41Z
data/gaspol/bham-city_pmch-pmcp-release_000802.na | md5 | 1e376f3d01c6e3e886f5bfe6645fff1bf | 5609 | 2003-02-13T17:03:03Z
data/gaspol/bham-city_pmch-release_000201.na | md5 | 4d0ca45034b8221ad3372b22614f85fe | 12542 | 2003-02-13T17:03:03Z
data/gaspol/bham-city_pmch-release_990701.na | md5 | 042f5048265447aa6cb1cc664335e341 | 24701 | 2003-02-13T17:03:03Z
data/gaspol/bham-city_pmch_000201.na | md5 | d0ead636df3e27b0bcf29d373521f1b6 | 6230 | 2003-02-13T17:03:03Z
data/gaspol/bham-city_pmch_990701.na | md5 | a1e252301fbff3b350b3533317deae72 | 4346 | 2003-02-13T17:03:03Z
# DIR /datacentre/archvol/pan2/archive/urgent/data/phytox
# DIR /datacentre/archvol/pan2/archive/urgent/data/phytox/2001-04-27
data/phytox/2001-04-27/car_pm10-institution | md5 | 9b74... | 10...
data/phytox/2001-04-27/car_pm10-institution | md5 | 29a8fd... | 11...
data/phytox/2001-04-27/car_pm10-institution | md5 | 09f755... | 12...
data/phytox/2001-04-27/car_pm10-institution | md5 | 010430... | 13...
data/phytox/2001-04-27/car_pm10-institution | md5 | 685523916de702aeb07df197fab651a | 6468 | 2003-02-22T22:25:03Z
data/phytox/2001-04-27/car_pm10-toxicity | md5 | 010430... | 14...
data/phytox/2001-04-27/car_rat-weight | md5 | 098e5e1f6e4eeF006794d2fb7e4e5a63 | 1816 | 2003-02-22T22:10:54Z
data/phytox/00README | md5 | c19ece966db83465cf1441886315aa11 | 318 | 2003-02-21T22:51:47Z
```

Fixity - the state of being unchanging or permanent

File set and audit database

These screen shots from the CEDA database show how information from audits is recorded and analysed.

The screenshots show the CEDA database administration interface. The top screenshot displays an audit report for a specific file set, including details on the storage path, fileset, and partition. The bottom screenshot shows an audit comparison table with columns for audit number, state, total files, total volume, new files, deleted files, modified files, unchanged files, start/end times, and corrupt files.

Hardware Used

- JASMIN offers petascale storage, batch compute and cloud computing for big data challenges in environmental science, hosted at STFC Rutherford Appleton Laboratory in the UK.
- Lotus is the batch compute service provided JASMIN, with around 3000 cores available.
- The CEDA archive uses the Panasas petascale parallel storage as the primary storage for its archive.
- The CEDA info database is hosted on a virtual machine hosted on JASMIN

Further Information

- JASMIN data analysis facility: <http://jasmin.ac.uk/>
- CEDA: <http://www.ceda.ac.uk/>
- Sam.pepler@stfc.ac.uk
- Checkm spec: J. Kunza, S Abrams, D Loy, Checkm: a checksum-based manifest format (v0.7), 2010, <http://www.cdlib.org/services/uc3/docs/checkmspec.html>